

Research Article

Double Acceptance Sampling Plans Based on Truncated Life Tests for the Inverse Rayleigh Distribution

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Abstract

Double acceptance sampling plans was developed using the Inverse Rayleigh Distribution (IRD) as a model for the life time random variable for a truncated life test. In this paper, the single acceptance sampling developed by Rosaiah and Kantam (2005) has been extended to double acceptance sampling in terms of finding the minimum number of sample sizes necessary to ensure the specified average life time under a given consumer's risk. The probability of acceptance using the cumulative distribution function of IRD is calculated for different consumer's confidence levels with fixed producer's risk. The operating characteristic curves of the sampling plans as well as the tables are presented.

Keywords: Double Acceptance Sampling, Probability of Acceptance, Lots sentencing, Consumer's risk, Producer's risk, Inverse Rayleigh distribution.

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Introduction

Acceptance sampling is an inspection procedure in statistical quality control used to determine whether to accept or reject a specific quantity of material. The methods of statistical acceptance sampling is one of the most interesting and useful applications of modern mathematical statistics (John 1947). It involves probabilistic distributions and principle of experimental design which provide a ground for these theories to validate basic assumptions in more verifiable and correct inference, than in many biometric and

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sociometric applications (Montgomery, 2009). Even though the acceptance sampling continually faces many challenges, among the challenges is the requirement to improve product quality while lowering production cost. Acceptance sampling is one of the oldest statistical quality control tool; its development encompasses the concept of protecting the consumer from getting unacceptable defective material. It also protects the producer in the sense that lots produced at a permissible level of quality have a good chance to be accepted by the plan. Acceptance sampling procedures are necessary defensive measures, instituted as protective devices against the threat of deterioration in quality. As such, they should be set up with the aim of discontinuance in favour of process control procedures as soon as possible. In response to these challenges, much effort has been given to finding new technological tools (Schilling and Neubauer, 2008). Montgomery (2009) highlighted three basic approaches to lot sentencing: (1) accepting without inspection; (2) 100% inspection i.e. removing all defective units found; and (3) acceptance sampling. However, upon all the approaches, acceptance sampling is regarded as the most likely useful, especially when the cost of 100% inspecting a product is extremely high, and there may be serious product liability risks of rejecting the lot. Acceptance sampling is based on probability procedure and is the most widely used sampling technique. Many sampling plans are tabled and published; it can be used with little guidance due to the simplicity of these tables. The Dodge-Romig sampling inspection tables are an example of published tables.

Life tests are experiments carried out in order to obtain the lifetime of an item, that is the time of failure before its suppose time. The common practice in life tests is to terminate the test as soon as the number of acceptance is reached. In many situations, the quality of a product is measured through the life time (t_0) and the variance or the scale parameter of a distribution may serve as a quality parameter.

In this paper, we are interested in developing double acceptance sampling by finding the minimum number of samples sizes n_1 and n_2 necessary to assert that a life of a product meet the required specification. The probability of acceptance will also be calculated and some example to illustrate the importance of the lot sentencing in double sampling is presented.

The problems of determining the minimum number of sample size that will give assurances at a specified time remain the major challenge in the area of acceptance sampling plans. Several works regarding this can be found in Espstein (1954), Voda (1972), Mukherjee and Saran (1984), Mukherjee and Maiti (1997), Aslam and Jun (2009) as well as Fan and China (2015).

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All these authors consider the design of single acceptance sampling plans based on the population mean under truncated life test. Although Aslam and Jun (2009) developed a group acceptance sampling based on the inverse Rayleigh distribution, but the actual interplay remains single acceptance sampling from their practical delineation of the relationship.

Rosaiah and Kantam (2005) developed an acceptance sampling procedure for the inverse Rayleigh distribution mean under a truncated life test. Although, the work tries to address the problem of producer's risk by determining the minimum number of sample size necessary to give assurances for accepting the lot but it only uses one sample size. These reasons serve as motivation to developing double acceptance sampling plans based on the population means of the inverse Rayleigh distribution. It is known that the double acceptance sampling plan is more efficient than the single sampling plan in terms of the sample size required. (Sudamani and Sutharani, 2013).

Among the objectives of this paper is to set a lower confidence limit on the average life, it is desired also establish a specified average life with a given probability for at least p^* . To obtain the minimum sample sizes n_1 and n_2 necessary to achieve these objectives.

1. Inverse Rayleigh Distribution

Studies on the inverse Rayleigh distribution in the area of acceptance sampling are limited as there are few research conducted. The inverse Rayleigh distribution has many applications in the area of reliability studies, and it is the most important lifetime distribution (Fan and China, 2015). Voda (1972) mentioned that the distribution of lifetimes of several types of experimental units can be approximated by the inverse Rayleigh distribution. Most problems encountered in this plan is determining the minimum sample size from a lot for consideration (Aslam and Jun, 2009). The purpose of this research is to extend the work of Rosaiah and Kantam (2005) that uses the single sampling plan based on the inverse Rayleigh distribution to double sampling plan and possibly to also extend the work to multiple sampling plans, thereby finding the minimum numbers of sample sizes necessary to assure a certain average life when the life test is terminated at a pre-assigned time (t) and when the observed number of failures does not exceed a given acceptance number.

The cumulative distribution function (cdf) of an inverse Rayleigh distribution is given by

$$F(t; \dagger) = e^{-\left(\frac{t^2}{\dagger^2}\right)} ; t \geq 0, \dagger > 0 \quad (1)$$

where $\dagger > 0$ is the scaled parameter.

The density function of inverse Rayleigh distribution is given by

$$f(t; \dagger) = \frac{2t^2}{\dagger^3} e^{-\frac{t^2}{\dagger^2}} ; t \geq 0, \dagger > 0 \quad (2)$$

failure rate of an inverse Rayleigh distribution was studied by Mukherjee and Saran (1984) and found that the single parameter inverse Rayleigh is increasing for $t < 1.069\dagger$ and also decreasing for $t > 1.069\dagger$.

2. Double Acceptance Sampling Plan (DASP)

The DASP is used to minimise the risk of the producer, because it provides another opportunity for acceptance in case the rejection occur in single sampling plan. The consumer's risk which is the probability of accepting a bad lot when in the actual sense is supposed to be accepted. Let p^* be a minimum confidence level with which a lot having a true average life below is rejected by the sampling plan. For a given p^* our sampling plan is characterized by four parameters (n_1, n_2, c_1, c_2) as will explain later. We consider sufficiently large lots so that the binomial distribution can be applied. The interest is to determine for a given values of $p^*, \dagger_0, c_1,$ and c_2 , the smallest positive integer n such that

$$P(A) = C_0^{n_1} p^0 q^{n_1} + C_1^{n_1} p^1 q^{n_1-1} \left[\sum_{i=0}^1 C_i^{n_2} p^i q^{n_2-i} \right] \times C_2^{n_1} p^2 q^{n_1-2} [C_0^{n_2} p^0 q^{n_2}] \leq 1 - p^* \quad (3)$$

where $p = F(t; \dagger) = F\left(\frac{t}{\dagger_0} * \frac{\dagger_0}{\dagger}\right)$, is given by (1) indicates the failure before time t which depends only on the ratio $\frac{t}{\dagger}$ and is sufficient to specify this ratio for designing the experiment.

We propose the following DASP procedure based on truncated life test:

1. Draw the 1st sample of size n_1 and put them on test during time t
2. Accept the lots if there are no more than c_1 failures, else reject the lot if there are more than c_2 failures.
3. If the number of failures is between c_1 and c_2 , then draw the 2nd sample of size n_2 and put them on test during time t .

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4. Accept the lot if the total number of failures is not more than c_2 during time t .

The DASP comprises of four parameters (n_1, n_2, c_1, c_2) if time t_0 is specified. Here n_1 and n_2 refers to 1st and 2nd sample, while c_1 and c_2 refers to the acceptance numbers associated with the 1st and 2nd sample, respectively. Let \dagger be the unknown average life and \dagger_0 be the specified average life. A lot is considered good and worthy of acceptance if the true unknown average life is more than the specified average life. Likewise, the lot is considered bad if the true unknown average life is less than the specified average life. Consider a life testing experiment having n_1 items in the 1st sample with an acceptance number $c_1 = 0$ and n_2 items in the 2nd sample with the corresponding acceptance number $c_2 = 2$. If no failure occurs in the 1st sample items put on test, we accept the lot. Probability of acceptance for these is calculated and placed in Table 3. If there is a difference between \dagger (the true unknown lifetime average) and that of the \dagger_0 (the specified lifetime average) of the product, it can be obtained by probability of acceptance $L(p_1)$ and $L(p_2)$ for sampling plans $(n_1, c_1, \dagger/\dagger_0)$ and $(n_2, c_2, \dagger/\dagger_0)$ respectively.

For the Inverse Rayleigh Distribution, the probability of acceptance (PA) is given by

$$L(p_1) = \sum_{i=0}^{c_1} \binom{n_1}{i} \left(\ell^{-(\dagger/\dagger_0)^2} \right)^i \left(1 - \ell^{-(\dagger/\dagger_0)^2} \right)^{n_1-i} \quad (4)$$

$$L(p_2) = \sum_{i=1}^{c_2} \binom{n_2}{i} \left(\ell^{-(\dagger/\dagger_0)^2} \right)^i \left(1 - \ell^{-(\dagger/\dagger_0)^2} \right)^{n_2-i} \quad (5)$$

The producer's risk is the probability of rejecting the lot when $\dagger > \dagger_0$.

The probability of acceptance for a DASP is calculated and placed in Table 3 using 4 and 5.

The minimum values of n satisfying equation 3 were obtained for $1-r = 0.75, 0.9, 0.95, 0.99$ and $\dagger/\dagger_0 = 1.0, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, 2.0, 2.25, 2.50, 3.0$. These choices are consistent with Gupta and Groll (1961), Kantam and Rosaiah (1998), Baklizi and El-Masri (2004), Aslam (2007) and Rao (2015).

3. Proposed Double Acceptance Sampling Plan

In this section, we provide the acceptance sampling plans given by Rosaiah and Kantam (2005) and compared it our proposed double sampling plan.

Wood (1996) in predicting software reliability produces four major releases of defect detective results. Release 1 - 4. Rosaiah and Kantam (2005) and also Rao *et al* (2008) considers Release 1 and analyzed the data from the acceptance sampling view point using single acceptance sampling. In this research, we consider Release 4 and applied the double acceptance sampling view point using inverse Raleigh distribution. Let us consider the ordered sample of size $n = 14$ from time T (in hours)

$t_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, 14$): 254, 788, 1054, 1393, 2216, 2880, 3593, 4281, 5180, 6003, 7621, 8783, 9604, 10064

In order to confirm that the given sample is generated by lifetime following at least approximately the inverse Rayleigh distribution, we have compared the sample quantiles and obtained the probability plot and found satisfactory agreement with p-value 0.36 (Figure 1).

Let the specified average life be 1000 hours and the testing time is 1500 this leads to ratio of 1.50 with the corresponding n and c as 10 and 2 respectively. Rosaiah and Kantam (2005) obtained an acceptable probability of 0.7687 which leads to accepting the product with only two (2) defectives.

Table1: Comparison of single and double sampling plan's operating characteristics values

0.95	1	1.25	1.5	1.75	2	2.25	2.5
For single	0.9895	0.9116	0.7687	0.4640	0.2970	0.5862	0.6455
For double	0.9309	0.4496	0.1140	0.0679	0.0214	0.0539	0.0732

From Table 1, one can easily see for the single sampling at 1.5, the probability of acceptance is 77% i.e the consumer will be willing to accept such a product. But for same timing, the double acceptance sampling yields just 11% probability of acceptance i.e. it is unlikely for the consumer to accept such as product. See Table 2 and 3.

Our test is implemented as follows: Select 14 items from the submitted lot of a product and reject this lot if more than 2 failures is recorded in this sample before the experiment time, but if the failure is less than 2 but greater than 0 proceed to second sample of 19 and reject the lot if more than 2 failures occurs before the experiment time, else if the time come first stop the testing and accept the lot.

In the proposed approach, we notice that in a sample of 19 lots there were only 2 failures obtained within the period of 11 hours. Therefore we accept the product with probability of acceptance 0.95. The most important thing to note here is our proposed plan is far more economical than the single sampling we compared with. This is because the in terms of timing too, whereas in the single sampling it took 77 hours before the decision is taken.

Figure 1: Probability plot for the Software release

Conclusion

We find the double acceptance sampling plans for various values of $\frac{1}{A_0}$ and the different experiment times assuming that the lifetime of a product follows the inverse Rayleigh distribution. The proposed plan yields the minimum termination ratio that is required to test the items to decide upon whether a submitted lot is good having an average life or not.

The proposed plan is useful in minimising the producer's risk likewise also considering the consumer's risk. Further, the decision on the single sampling approach can be reached at 77th hour but in the double sampling it was reached at the 11th hour, thus the proposed plan require less waiting time and also minimise the cost to reach the final decision about a lot of the product. Hence the proposed plan is more economical than the single sampling plan. It also puts pressure to the producer to make sure his products are up to standard since the test requires minimum time and minimum sample to reach a decision.

Table 2: Operating characteristic values for the single sampling plan with $c = 2$

p	n1	t/s	2	4	6	8
0.75	10	1	0.9993	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	7	1.25	0.9872	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	5	1.5	0.9631	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	5	1.75	0.8733	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	4	2	0.8558	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	4	2.25	0.7534	0.9997	1.0000	1.0000
	4	2.5	0.6455	0.9983	1.0000	1.0000
	4	3	0.4527	0.9831	1.0000	1.0000
0.9		t/s	2	4	6	8
	13	1	0.9985	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	17	1.25	0.8605	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	12	1.5	0.6691	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	9	1.75	0.5424	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	8	2	0.3859	0.9997	1.0000	1.0000
	5	2.25	0.5862	0.9993	1.0000	1.0000
	3	2.5	0.8534	0.9995	1.0000	1.0000
2	3	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	
0.95		t/s	2	4	6	8
	25	1	0.9895	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	14	1.25	0.9116	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	10	1.5	0.7687	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	10	1.75	0.4640	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	9	2	0.2970	0.9995	1.0000	1.0000
	5	2.25	0.5862	0.9993	1.0000	1.0000
	4	2.5	0.6455	0.9983	1.0000	1.0000
3	3	0.7364	0.9952	1.0000	1.0000	
0.99		t/s	2	4	6	8
	20	1	0.9945	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	15	1.25	0.8956	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	13	1.5	0.6190	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	8	1.75	0.6260	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	9	2	0.2970	0.9995	1.0000	1.0000
	5	2.25	0.5862	0.9993	1.0000	1.0000
	4	2.5	0.6455	0.9983	1.0000	1.0000
3	3	0.7364	0.9952	1.0000	1.0000	

Table 3: Operating characteristic values for the double sampling plan with (n_2, c_2, t_0) when $c_1=0$ and $c_2=2$

P	n1	n2	t/s	2	4	6	8
0.75	15	30	1	0.9637	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	9	18	1.25	0.7290	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	8	16	1.5	0.3224	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	10	20	1.75	0.0453	0.9996	1.0000	1.0000
	7	14	2	0.0432	0.9953	1.0000	1.0000
	6	12	2.25	0.0278	0.9711	1.0000	1.0000
	5	10	2.5	0.0247	0.9201	1.0000	1.0000
	5	10	3	0.0060	0.6139	0.9982	1.0000
0.9	n1	n2	t/s	2	4	6	8
	19	37	1	0.9378	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	17	34	1.25	0.3610	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	12	24	1.5	0.1302	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	9	18	1.75	0.0643	0.9997	1.0000	1.0000
	8	16	2	0.0264	0.9932	1.0000	1.0000
	7	14	2.25	0.0148	0.9571	1.0000	1.0000
	7	15	2.5	0.0053	0.8199	1.0000	1.0000
6	11	3	0.0021	0.5257	0.9974	1.0000	
0.95	n1	n2	t/s	2	4	6	8
	25	30	1	0.9309	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	18	22	1.25	0.4496	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	14	19	1.5	0.1140	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	10	12	1.75	0.0679	0.9998	1.0000	1.0000
	9	11	2	0.0214	0.9952	1.0000	1.0000
	5	10	2.25	0.0539	0.9822	1.0000	1.0000
	4	6	2.5	0.0732	0.9689	1.0000	1.0000
3	5	3	0.0635	0.8819	0.9997	1.0000	
0.99	n1	n2	t/s	2	4	6	8
	30	35	1	0.8981	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	10	20	1.25	0.6761	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	13	26	1.5	0.1046	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	15	30	1.75	0.0088	0.9987	1.0000	1.0000
	9	18	2	0.0164	0.9905	1.0000	1.0000
	8	16	2.25	0.0080	0.9404	1.0000	1.0000
	7	14	2.5	0.0053	0.8318	1.0000	1.0000
6	12	3	0.0021	0.5013	0.9970	1.0000	

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